

The association of pornography usage and relationship satisfaction in heterosexual romantic relationships

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Objective: To systematically collect current data that correlates pornography usage and relationship satisfaction and determine and qualify the direction and magnitude of correlation if applicable.

Methods: The PubMed data base was searched and retrieved 611 papers of which 580 were excluded after title and abstract screening. The remaining 31 papers were full text screened resulting in 6 papers being selected for analysis.

Findings: Across the 6 papers there was a total of 17,114 individuals (7,058 males and 10,056 females) who were in heterosexual romantic relationships. All papers utilized online survey methods. From the statistically significant data, the average correlation coefficient was $r = -0.185$ indicating a weak negative correlation.

Conclusion: The overall strength and significance of the negative correlation between pornography usage can not academically be stated as strong, but needs to be acknowledged as negative, nevertheless. Seeing as the human pair bond is a multi dimensional interaction, it is important to note that the papers reported other factors such as sexual satisfaction to be much more negatively correlated.

Introduction:

Pornography as material, in a metaphysical sense, is *consumed* by individuals and thus it is pertinent to ask relevant questions on why individuals use it and what its effects are on a person. The prevalence of pornography usage is growing with its increasing accessibility in the digital age. Within developed countries such as the United States and Australia, the majority of the male population (64–70%) and approximately one quarter/third (23–33%) of women are using pornography [3]. In developing nations, recent surveys have shown that over half of the students in Ethiopia and Bangladesh have been exposed

to Pornography [4]. Pornhub, one of the largest online pornographic websites, reports its primary users to be males (74%), and that the number of visitors to pornographic sites is growing from year to year [5].

An individual's pornography use may stem from the inherent satisfaction in engaging with the sexual self. The *sexual strategies theory* of Buss and Schmitt theorises the evolutionary aspect of human mating behaviour in respect to short-term and long-term mating. The prior of these mating strategies is characterized by frequency of intercourse without emotional investment, a physical expression and

release of sexual desire without a focus of the long-term nature of a committed romantic relationship, something pornography (and self stimulation) can facilitate. In a non-exhaustive itemized list it is said that pornography is consumed because of: (1) increased sex drive, (2) enhancing sexual performance, (3) social and instrumental reasons, and (4) lack of relational and emotional skills. [7]

This nature of pornography usage and its relation to the sexual component of the human animal links it to (in a primitive sense) the realm of mating, which may better be presented as pair-bonded relationships. It is pertinent to investigate the association of pornography on the physiological, psychological, and

sociological aspect of these relationships. Previous studies have investigated the association of pornography consumption on an individual's sexual desire, disfunction, and satisfaction. Another group of studies approached the topic in respect to the relationship and bonding between partners themselves, discussing things such as communication, aggression, and overall relationship satisfaction. The last of these topics, the association of pornography on relationship satisfaction, has yielded mixed results in respect to effect size and in some instances, direction of correlation.

The purpose of this study is to systematically review the literature containing data on the association of pornography on relationship satisfaction.

Methods:

2.1 Search Strategy

The preliminary search strategy was based on Population/Intervention/Comparison/Outcomes/Study Design (PICOS) with the review question: What is the association between pornography usage and relationship satisfaction in heterosexual romantic relationships. The PubMed, database was systematically reviewed from the inception of the database searching until the date of the current search. Furthermore, there will be no restrictions regarding the language. The search strategy was implemented on November 17th, 2021. The search strategy contained critical terms according to the pre-established PICOS acronym. One independent researcher (S.I) implement the

search strategy in the PubMed database. It should be noted that all keywords in the PubMed database were identified with their synonyms. The search terms were combined using the Boolean operators "AND" and "OR." (Supplementary Table 1).

2.2 Study Selection

Study selection was based on the PICOS search strategy shown in Supplementary Table 2.

Inclusion Criteria:

Studies that included data on the effect/association of pornography on relationship satisfaction in heterosexual

romantic relationships in both sexes were selected; all ages and ethnicities were included in the study.

Exclusion Criteria:

Papers were excluded if they focused, on the association of pornography on sexual satisfaction or on the effect of religiosity on the association of pornography on relationship satisfaction. Other reasons of exclusion included

papers by the same authors with the same datasets but were published under various titles based on the sub analysis that was done. Papers which included populations of homosexual couples were excluded if multivariable analysis (ANOVA) was not done to isolate heterosexual couples.

2.3 Outcome Measures:

The primary outcome measure was the effect of pornography use on relationship satisfaction.

2.4 Assessment of Methodological quality:

Critical appraisal for assessing the study paper's methodological quality was

Figure 1

performed using the STROBE (Strengthening the Reporting of Observational Studies in Epidemiology) combined checklist [1]. The STROBE checklist for appraisal of observational studies (cohort, case-control, and cross sectional) consisted of detailed recording of title/abstract, introduction, methods, results, discussion, and other information.

Data Analysis:

An independent reviewer (S.I) exported the data from each study into an Excel sheet. Effect sizes which used a correlation coefficient were summed together to estimate an average.

Table 1.

Reference	Study Type	Country	Group	Age (years)
McNabney et al 2020	Online Survey	United States	966 females	mean age = 28.72, range = 18–95
	Online Survey	Hungary	1043 females	
	Pencil-Paper	Hungary	424 females	
Willoughby and Leonhardt 2018	Online Survey	United states	240 heterosexual couples	male mean age = 34.7 female mean age = 32.9
SL Perry 2020	2 National Studies NFSSL RIA	United States	NFSSL: Males: 915 Females: 1,062 Total: 1,977	NFSSL: Male mean age: 29.4 Female Mean age: 28.9 Total Range: 18-39
			RIA: Males: 4,998 Females: 5,109 Total: 10,106	RIA: Male mean age: 41.3 Female Mean age: 40.2 Total Range: 18-60
Minarcik 2016	Online Survey	United States	Males: 75 Females: 221 Total: 296	Mean age: 28.51
Shuler 2021	Online Survey	United States	Males: 214 Females: 374 Total: 588	Mean age: 25.72
Poulsen et al 2013	Online Survey	Western United States	617 heterosexual couples	Male mean age: 32 Female Mean age: 29 Total Range: 17-58

Table 2.

Reference	Measure of Pornography Use	Measure of Relationship Satisfaction
McNabney et al 2020	0 = I do not use erotic materials, 1 = only several times a year, 2 = less than once a month, 3 = several times a month, 4 = several times a week, 5 = several times a day	5-point Likert 1 (very dissatisfied) to 5 (very satisfied)
Willoughby and Leonhardt 2018	Personal Use: Confirmation via displaying examples of erotic material consumed Couple Use: Responses ranged from 1 (I never watch pornography) To 6 (0% alone, 100% together)	5-point Likert 1 (very dissatisfied) to 5 (very satisfied)
SL Perry 2020	NFSSL: 1 = Never to 6 = Every day or almost every day. RIA: 1 = Today to 10 = I've never intentionally looked at pornography.	NFSSL and RIA: 1 = Very unhappy to 10 = Perfectly happy
Minarcik 2016	Hours/month	DAS-7 (9 Likert style items) 0 (distressed) to 36 (non-distressed).
Shuler 2021	Reported intentionally accessing pornography in the past month	Participants were asked to qualitatively respond to the prompt "In your own words how has pornography influenced your relationship and/or sexual satisfaction." To identify common themes
Poulsen et al 2013	"During the last twelve months, on how many days did you view or read pornography" Were on a 6-point, Likert-type scale ranging from 1 (never) to 6 (almost every day).	5-point Likert 1 (very dissatisfied) to 5 (very satisfied)

Results:

3.1 Description of studies

The search strategy in supplementary table 1 retrieved 611 papers. From the 611 papers, based on title and abstract, 31 papers, on preliminary examination, discussed research on the association of pornography on relationship satisfaction. From the 31 papers, full-text screening yielded 6 papers that truly contained research on the association of pornography on relationship satisfaction in heterosexual couples. A total of 25 papers were excluded after the full-text screening for various reasons detailed in fig.1.

Across the 6 papers there was a total of 17,114 individuals (7,058 males and 10,056 females) who were in heterosexual romantic relationships. McNabney et al 2020 took a sample of purely female participants and thus is one of the factors that contributes to an overall greater female sample size. Over all the studies 91.4% (15,647) of the sample was from the United States and the remaining 8.6% (1,467) of participants were from Hungary. All 5 of the 6 papers primarily used an online survey to collect data with the only exception being SL Perry 2020 who used data from 2 national studies conducted in the United States

4 of the 6 papers recorded pornography usage as various scales to indicate rough usage ranging from never having watched it to consuming it daily. Minarcik 2016 quantified usage of pornography by hours per month. The

research by Shuler 2021 was more open-ended. Participants were asked questions on their attitudes and thoughts on how pornography affected their relationships in general and pornography use was recorded by asking if there was use within a one-month timeframe.

3 of the 6 papers recorded relationship satisfaction using a 5-point Likert scale, ranging from 1 as very dissatisfied with their relationship to 5 as being very satisfied with their relationship. SL Perry 2020 used the 10-point scale used by the NFSSL and RIA (national surveys) where 1 was very unhappy with the relationship and 10 was perfectly happy with the relationship. Minarcik 2016 used the DAS-7 (9 Likert style items) which resulted in a scale from 0 as being distressed with the relationship to 36 as being non-distressed with the relationship. As mentioned prior, Shuler 2021 had a more open-ended approach and thus relationship satisfaction and other metrics were recorded in the form of long responses which were then grouped via thematic analysis.

Two papers used advanced quantitative methodology via SEM (structural equational modeling) and thus calculated effects in respect to the various variables that were known to contribute to the interaction between pornography use and relationship satisfaction, such as sex, religiosity, moral attitudes, and socio-economic status. Two papers used ordinal logistic regression, 1 paper used an ANOVA, and 1 paper used thematic grouping.

Table 3.

Reference	Statics	Findings
McNabney et al 2020	Ordinal Regression Effect size: Cohen's d	Pornography Use: Yes: RS: Mean:4.07 No: RS: Mean: 4.09 Effect Size: 0.024 p=0.619
Willoughby and Leonhardt 2018	SEM Effect size: r value *Dyadic approach	Male Pornography Use: Male RS: r= -0.29** p<0.01 Female RS: r= -0.26** p<0.01 Female Pornography Use: Female RS: r= -0.06 Male RS: r= -0.09
SL Perry 2020	Ordinal Logistic Regression Effect size: r value	NFSS r= -0.12 p<0.001
		RIA r= -0.07 P<0.001
Minarcik 2016	ANOVA analysis	Non-use: Mean RS: 25.22 Individual Use: Mean RS: 23.19 Shared User: Mean RS: 25.25 relationship satisfaction [F (2, 252) = 3.69, p = .026]

Shuler 2021	Thematic grouping	N=154 Reported detrimental effects to relationship satisfaction N= 317 Reported neural or mixed effects on relationship satisfaction.
Poulsen et al 2013	SEM Effect size: r value	Male Pornography Use: Male RS: r= -0.06 Female RS: r= -0.1 Female Pornography Use: Female RS: r= -0.06 Male RS: r= 0.05

3.2 Relationship satisfaction

From the 3 papers that used the Pearson product-moment correlation coefficient (PPMCC) the average correlation between pornography uses and relationship satisfaction was $r = -0.0116$. From papers stratified for gender, the average correlation coefficient for males was $r = -0.175$ and for females $r = -0.06$. From the statistically significant data, the average correlation coefficient was $r = -0.185$. Although not statistically significant ($p = 0.619$), McNabney et al 2020 reported a Cohen's d value of 0.024. The paper by Shuler 2021 thematically reported individuals ($n=154$) having detrimental effects from pornography use which negatively effected their relationship satisfaction. Common complaints were of, feelings of inadequacy, decreases intimacy, feelings of betrayal, and the setting of unrealistic expectations.

4. Discussion

Across all 6 papers there was an overall negative correlation between pornography usage and relationship

satisfaction. From the statistically significant data from amongst the papers that used the PPMCC the correlation coefficient was an average of an $r = -0.185$. This r value suggests a weak to low negative relationship between pornography viewership and relationship satisfaction. There was no statistically significant data that showed a positive correlation between pornography usage and relationship satisfaction. In respect to gendered defences there were mixed reports either showed a proportionally higher negative correlation in men compared to woman or showing that there is no difference in correlation. Willoughby and Leonhardt 2018 reported that men had an $r = -0.29$ and woman had an $r = -0.06$, showing a much greater negative correlation in men. Poulsen et al 2013 show that both men and woman have an $r = -0.06$. It is pertinent to know that only the r of -0.29 in men is statistically significant. Papers that took a dyadic approach (Willoughby and Leonhardt 2018, Poulsen et al 2013) show that male pornography use is not only negatively correlated with their own personal relationship satisfaction but also is

negatively correlated with female relationship satisfaction.

There are several aspects that affect relationship satisfaction and thus these become cofounders towards the true interaction between pornography usage and relationship satisfaction. Papers that utilized structural equation modeling (Willoughby and Leonhardt 2018, Poulsen et al 2013) were able to mitigate confounding bias caused by gender, religiosity/moral disapproval, age, race, depression, and other specific markers of relationship quality such as communication.

As a general comment, a limitation of these observational studies in psychological humanities research is that there will always be unaccounted for confounding variables which are deeply rooted in each individual's personal circumstance. Furthermore, due to the data

being through surveys and pertaining to taboo topics there is a great possibility for self reporting bias. Although, to a degree, online surveys help to mitigate some of the awkwardness that may arise when speaking to a researcher directly.

5. Conclusion

In light of this particular paper's limited scope and resources it can be concluded that the overall strength and significance of the negative correlation between pornography usage cannot academically be stated as strong, but needs to be acknowledged as negative, nonetheless. However, seeing as the human pair bond is a multi dimensional interaction it is important to note that the papers reported other factors such as sexual satisfaction to be much more negatively correlated. [9]

Supplementary Tables:

TABLE 1. Concepts and search items

Database	Search items
PubMed (Entered search)	((Romantic Relationship) OR (Relationship) OR (Adult pair bond) OR (Marriage) OR (Intimate relationships)) AND ((Pornography) OR (Porn) OR (Sexually explicit material) OR (SEM) OR (Sexual media) OR (Erotica) OR (Visual sexual stimuli) OR (VSS) OR (Cybersex) OR (Online sexual activity))) AND ((Satisfaction) OR (Happiness) OR (Pleasure))
PubMed (Automatically generated expanded search)	((("romantic"[All Fields] OR "romantically"[All Fields] OR "romantics"[All Fields]) AND ("relationship"[All Fields] OR "relationships"[All Fields])) OR ("relationship"[All Fields] OR "relationships"[All Fields]) OR (("adult"[MeSH Terms] OR "adult"[All Fields] OR "adults"[All Fields] OR "adult s"[All Fields]) AND ("pair bond"[MeSH Terms] OR ("pair"[All Fields] AND "bond"[All Fields]) OR "pair bond"[All Fields])) OR ("marriage"[MeSH Terms] OR "marriage"[All Fields] OR "marriages"[All Fields] OR "marriageability"[All Fields] OR "marriageable"[All Fields]) OR (("intimate"[All Fields] OR "intimates"[All Fields]) AND ("relationship"[All Fields] OR "relationships"[All Fields]))) AND ("erotica"[MeSH Terms] OR "erotica"[All Fields] OR "pornography"[All Fields] OR "Porn"[All Fields] OR (("sexual behavior"[MeSH Terms] OR ("sexual"[All Fields] AND "behavior"[All Fields]) OR "sexual behavior"[All Fields] OR "sexual"[All Fields] OR "sexually"[All Fields] OR "sexualities"[All Fields] OR "sexuality"[MeSH Terms] OR "sexuality"[All Fields] OR "sexualization"[All Fields] OR "sexualize"[All Fields] OR "sexualized"[All Fields] OR "sexualizing"[All Fields] OR "sexuals"[All Fields]) AND ("explicit"[All Fields] OR "explicitness"[All Fields]) AND ("material"[All Fields] OR "material s"[All Fields] OR "materials"[All Fields])) OR ("struct equ modeling"[Journal] OR "scan electron microsc"[Journal] OR "sem"[All Fields]) OR (("sexual behavior"[MeSH Terms] OR ("sexual"[All Fields] AND "behavior"[All Fields]) OR "sexual behavior"[All Fields] OR "sexual"[All Fields] OR "sexually"[All Fields] OR "sexualities"[All Fields] OR "sexuality"[MeSH Terms] OR "sexuality"[All Fields] OR "sexualization"[All Fields] OR "sexualize"[All Fields] OR "sexualized"[All Fields] OR "sexualizing"[All Fields] OR "sexuals"[All Fields]) AND ("culture media"[Pharmacological Action] OR "culture media"[MeSH Terms] OR ("culture"[All Fields] AND "media"[All Fields]) OR "culture

Database**Search items**

media"[All Fields] OR "media"[All Fields] OR "media s"[All Fields] OR "medias"[All Fields])) OR ("erotica"[MeSH Terms] OR "erotica"[All Fields]) OR (("visual"[All Fields] OR "visualisation"[All Fields] OR "visualisations"[All Fields] OR "visualise"[All Fields] OR "visualised"[All Fields] OR "visualises"[All Fields] OR "visualising"[All Fields] OR "visualization"[All Fields] OR "visualizations"[All Fields] OR "visualize"[All Fields] OR "visualized"[All Fields] OR "visualizer"[All Fields] OR "visualizers"[All Fields] OR "visualizes"[All Fields] OR "visualizing"[All Fields] OR "visually"[All Fields] OR "visuals"[All Fields]) AND ("sexual behavior"[MeSH Terms] OR ("sexual"[All Fields] AND "behavior"[All Fields]) OR "sexual behavior"[All Fields] OR "sexual"[All Fields] OR "sexually"[All Fields] OR "sexualities"[All Fields] OR "sexuality"[MeSH Terms] OR "sexuality"[All Fields] OR "sexualization"[All Fields] OR "sexualize"[All Fields] OR "sexualized"[All Fields] OR "sexualizing"[All Fields] OR "sexuals"[All Fields]) AND ("stimuli"[All Fields] OR "stimuli s"[All Fields] OR "stimulis"[All Fields])) OR "VSS"[All Fields] OR "Cybersex"[All Fields] OR ("Online"[All Fields] AND ("sexual behavior"[MeSH Terms] OR ("sexual"[All Fields] AND "behavior"[All Fields]) OR "sexual behavior"[All Fields] OR ("sexual"[All Fields] AND "activity"[All Fields]) OR "sexual activity"[All Fields])) AND ("personal satisfaction"[MeSH Terms] OR ("personal"[All Fields] AND "satisfaction"[All Fields]) OR "personal satisfaction"[All Fields] OR "satisfaction"[All Fields] OR "satisfactions"[All Fields] OR "satisfaction s"[All Fields] OR ("happi"[All Fields] OR "happiness"[MeSH Terms] OR "happiness"[All Fields] OR "happy"[All Fields]) OR ("pleasurability"[All Fields] OR "pleasurable"[All Fields] OR "pleasurableness"[All Fields] OR "pleasure"[MeSH Terms] OR "pleasure"[All Fields] OR "pleasures"[All Fields] OR "pleasuring"[All Fields]))

TABLE 2. Inclusion and exclusion criteria

PICOS acronym	Inclusion criteria	Exclusion criteria
P—Population	Both sexes, all ages, and any ethnicity	None
	In a romantic relationship	Non-romantic relationships
	Heterosexual	Homosexual
I—Intervention/Exposure	Pornography use	
C—Comparison	None	None
O—Outcome	Relationship satisfaction	Sexual satisfaction
S—Study Design	All study designs	
Language	English	Other than English

Citations

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